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A new scalable methodology to predict permeability of deformed textiles under compression

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Motivation

Prescale pressure film

PRESCALE®: a pressure sensitive film by FujiFilm.

When a force is applied, **shades of color** appear according to the pressure experienced

Pressure prints from compressing different fabric architectures: Twill, NCF, Distribution medium

Prescale film characteristics:

- cost effective
- no domain size limitations
- can be put in non-planar molds

Pressure → Geometry

Extract information from the pressure field to reconstruct the textile architecture

Methodology

Geometrical variability

Variability in aspect ratio of yarns [6,7]

UDT400 glass quasi-ud fabric

light source

yarn

compression plates

Force cell

Acquired yarn profile

Cross section area variability

Aspect ratio variability

Confocal scanner apparatus

Cross section area variability

How much variability is there in cross section area?

Yarn profile described by power ellipse [8]:

$$S(t)_x = \frac{w_0}{2} \cos(2\pi t) \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1$$

$$S(t)_y = \begin{cases} \frac{h_0}{2} (\sin(2\pi t))^n & 0 \leq t \leq 0.5 \\ -\frac{h_0}{2} (-\sin(2\pi t))^n & 0.5 \leq t \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

w_0 = width, h_0 = thickness, $n = 0.3$ (shape factor)

In a population of 9 measured yarns:

- Mean Area: $\bar{A}_0 = 1.06 \text{ mm}^2$
- StDev: $\sigma = 0.0198 \text{ mm}^2$ (2%)

Superimposed measured yarn cross sections

Assumption:

The yarn reference cross section area A_0 is **constant** and independent of the aspect ratio

Aspect ratio variability

Effect of aspect ratio on compaction pressure?

Prescale pressure film

Confocal scanner apparatus

light source

fabric

compression plates

Force cell

Thick & narrow yarn

Pressure field

The effect is clearly visible

Yarn mechanical model

Relate compression pressure to the aspect ratio

Continuum description of the yarn [9,10]

Constitutive law: Hyperfoam material (compressible hyperelastic) [11]

$$\Phi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3) = \frac{2\mu}{\alpha^2} \left(\lambda_1^\alpha + \lambda_2^\alpha + \lambda_3^\alpha - 3 + \frac{1}{\beta} (J^{-\alpha\beta} - 1) \right)$$

λ_i = principal stretches, $J = \det(\mathbf{F})$, α, β, μ = material parameters

$J \neq 1 \rightarrow$ compressibility

$$\sigma_i = \frac{\lambda_i}{J} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \lambda_i} \rightarrow \begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= \frac{2\mu}{\alpha \lambda_2} \left(\lambda_1^{\alpha-1} - \lambda_2^{-\alpha\beta} \lambda_1^{-\alpha\beta-1} \right) \\ \sigma_2 &= \frac{2\mu}{\alpha \lambda_1} \left(\lambda_2^{\alpha-1} - \lambda_1^{-\alpha\beta} \lambda_2^{-\alpha\beta-1} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Yarn characterization

- Free lateral expansion: $\sigma_1 = 0 \rightarrow \lambda_1 = \lambda_2^{-\frac{\beta}{1+\beta}}$
- Inextensibility of fibers: $\lambda_3 = 1$
- Constant reference cross section area

Parameters identified:
 $\alpha = 44.82, \beta = 0.18, \mu = 0.83 \text{ MPa}$

Compression device and yarn cross section

Numerical model to create material database

Relate aspect ratio to pressure

Assumption: $A_0 = \text{constant}$

Creation of a database: aspect ratio $\rightarrow \sigma_2$

Yarn dimensions identification

Each yarn on the print is treated separately

1. Pressure curve extracted
2. Value matched against $\sigma_2(w_0, h_0)$ database
3. Yarn dimensions **identified**

Validation

Specimen	w_0 measured	h_0 measured	w_0 predicted (error)	h_0 predicted (error)
1	2.94	0.35	3.192 (8.5%)	0.34 (2.8%)
2	3.39	0.33	3.392 (0.05%)	0.32 (3%)
3	2.7	0.41	2.65 (1.8%)	0.405 (1.2%)
4	2.7	0.41	2.77 (2.6%)	0.4 (4.8%)
5	3.42	0.34	3.392 (1%)	0.32 (5.8%)
6	2.75	0.39	2.855 (3.8%)	0.38 (2.6%)

Some deviations are present, due to:

Material parameters calibration

Stress state not very homogeneous

Prescale film sensitivity

Resolution limit on pressure field

Area assumption

Constant reference area

Yarn paths

Yarn path nodes extracted from print

Crossover points used as **markers**

Yarn paths are created by individual composite Bezier curves using the extracted nodes as control points

$$S(t) = P_1(1 - t)^3 + 3P_2t(1 - t)^2 + 3P_3t^2(1 - t) + P_4t^3, \quad t \in [0,1]$$

Textile reconstruction

Textile geometry computed using TexGen core module [8]:

Reconstructed UDT400 textile geometry (reference state)

Conclusions

Recreated geometry: **not idealized**

- Single layer: method demonstration
- Multi-layer: real applications

Future work: **multi-layer** case

- Yarn positions identification
- Intensity field $\rightarrow V_f$ field
- Pressure distribution on curved shapes/ribs
- Permeability map for flow simulations

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The poster features three circular images: a mammoth, a modern building, and a castle. The background is light blue with a geometric pattern and confetti.

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